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Social entrepreneurship for the empowerment of young people in Finland and Latvia – Evaluation of a transnational educational project

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**REACH FOR
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Introduction

This publication is written to evaluate a transnational project funded by the Interreg Central Baltic Programme and the European Union during 2023-2025. The project was conducted as an educational programme to increase the knowledge and skills of social entrepreneurship among young people in Finland and Latvia. The training programme was developed by Reach for Change, a non-profit organisation founded in Sweden. The organisation acts globally to promote social entrepreneurship as a viable form of gaining income, and the training programme was first conducted in Ethiopia and Ghana. This project was the pilot of the programme to be implemented in Europe among young people.

Reach for Change Baltics, a non-profit organisation based in Latvia and co-founded with headquarters in Sweden in 2014, is part of the organisation and the global network. It served as a leading partner and coordinator of this project, adjusting the original educational program and developing new training materials to serve young people, particularly. The training of young people was conducted by a Latvian non-profit association, Creative Ideas, and the Diaconia Institute (DILA), a vocational education institution based in Lahti, Finland. These organisations

contributed to the development of the programme by adapting the materials for local use and producing content for the programme, e.g. video lectures. Juvenia, Youth Research and Development Centre based at the South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences evaluated the functionality of the training programme with young people, the replicability of the training curriculum, and the societal impact of the project.

As the final publication of the project, this report presents the general outcomes of the educational program of social entrepreneurship and seeks to evaluate its wider impacts. In the policies of the European Union, it has been stated that entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship should be promoted more efficiently among young European people, especially those who live in rural and disadvantaged areas, to improve their employment prospects and to develop sustainable livelihoods (European Union, EU Youth Strategy, Employment and Entrepreneurship, read 4.4.2025). According to Flash Eurobarometer 513, conducted in 2022, the average willingness to be self-employed among youth aged 18-30 in the member states of the European Union was 39%. The rate was 40% in Latvia and 26% in Finland. (Social

Entrepreneurship and Youth, Country Factsheets, Read 4.4.2025.) Approximately 46% of young people in the EU were willing to set up their own business, but many risks were seen in it. Lack of capital and resources, financial risks, and insufficient entrepreneurial skills and knowledge were considered by young people to be the main barriers for them to start an enterprise. (Social Entrepreneurship and Youth, Read 4.4.2025.)

The overall insights given in the project “Social entrepreneurship for empowering young people in Finland and Latvia” (henceforth “SocEntYouth” according to the project’s acronym) reflected these results in a few respects, such as some differences between Finland and Latvia regarding the statuses of social entrepreneurship in these countries, regardless that all participants were trained with similar materials and facts on social entrepreneurship, closely following the educational programme provided by the leading partner.

In general, this project responded to the challenge of young people needing more knowledge and skills on entrepreneurship and sparked young people to adopt an entrepreneurial mindset. The original aim was to train 120 young people altogether during the timeline of the project, and 121 persons passed the course successfully. The training was implemented in three (3) separate training cycles arranged during 2024-2025, and the number of young people attending each cycle was 33-51.

This report is divided into three parts. In the first part, knowledge is provided on social entrepreneurship as a form of entrepreneurship and its status in contemporary Finland and Latvia. The aims of this transnational project are explained within the context of the need to improve the employment situation of young people in rural and disadvantaged areas at the EU level and, thus, the need to implement the programme in these two countries. In addition to this, research-based insights are provided on the cultural differences related to the functioning of social enterprises and to better understand the outcomes of the training.

The second part of the report provides a description of the implementation of the training programme and how the training on social entrepreneurship was perceived by the young people who participated in the training. It also provides a summary of the internal, mid-term evaluation done after the first training cycle, and what measures were taken to develop the training, as the internal evaluation and participant feedback were taken into consideration. Analyses of the quantitative and qualitative data of the participant feedback will be provided to visualise how the benefits of the training of all three cycles were perceived by young people.

The third part of the report provides an evaluation of the functionality of the training with Finnish and Latvian young people, such as those requiring

support in their employability and employment and those with fewer opportunities. The evaluation also reflects on the issues that would be worth consideration in terms of the replicability of the project, such as which factors should be taken into account when training young people. The report will conclude by reflecting on the outcomes of the project in relation to the

situation and prospects of young people in contemporary social and societal conditions, as well as at the European level. The report concludes with general recommendations regarding educational programmes promoting entrepreneurship and employability of young people on the basis of experiences gained from the SocEntYouth project.

PART 1

**Project aiming to improve
the employment and employability
of disadvantaged young people
in Finland and Latvia**

This part of the report provides general knowledge of social entrepreneurship and its relation to traditional entrepreneurship, and the status of social entrepreneurship in Finland and Latvia. It also provides research knowledge of the attitudes of young people in these countries, considering entrepreneurship as a potential option for the future. It also highlights the aims of the employment policies of the European Union to create more opportunities for young people to start with social entrepreneurship. More generally, enhancing the skills of young people for self-employment has been considered important, for example, in the European Union, to improve the employment situation of youth, especially in rural and disadvantaged areas. (European Union, EU Youth Strategy, Employment and Entrepreneurship, read 4.4.2025.) These reflections are followed by explaining the aims of this educational project to meet the needs of those, especially those who need support in their employment, such as those with lower levels of education.

1. The aims of the project related to social entrepreneurship and youth empowerment

The funding application for the project was drafted to respond to the annual funding call of Interreg Central Baltic in 2022, and it concerned the project's priority area of improved employment

opportunities in the labour market. SocEntYouth was accepted in winter 2023 to be funded from 1.4.2023 to 30.9.2025. According to the project proposal, the empowerment and better employability of disadvantaged young people in Finland and Latvia were the main targets. These aims involved particularly the efforts to improve the situation of NEET young people, meaning those not in education, employment or training. In Finland, the rate of NEETs in 2023 was 9.4% of young people aged 15-29, and in Latvia, the rate was 10 % (Eurostat, Statistics on Young People neither in Employment, Education or Training. Read 8.2.2025). Improving the employability of NEETs by training them with knowledge and skills of social entrepreneurship and improving their employability was defined as the basic aim of the SocEntYouth project.

According to the Finnish statistics and indicator bank Sotkanet.fi, unemployment among youth aged 15-24 in the Eastern Uusimaa and Päijät-Häme regions increased by approximately two percentage points from 2023 to 2024. By the end of 2024, the youth unemployment rate was 16.1 % in the Päijät-Häme region and 15.2 % in the Eastern Uusimaa region. In the whole country, the unemployment rate in 2024 was 13.2 % in that age cohort, and the increase from the year 2023 was 1.7 percentage points. At the national level and in all age cohorts, the unemployment rate increased by one per cent from 9.8 % to 10.8 %. (Sotkanet.fi, Results Table. Read 8.2.2025.)

According to labour market research, structural changes in working life have especially affected the situation of young people without education. Industrial workplaces have decreased, and the transition from an industrial to a service economy has happened gradually in only a few decades, especially influencing the Eastern parts of Finland (see e.g. Myrskylä 2012; Hiilamo & Aaltonen 2020). This development has decreased the opportunities of young men without education to find employment, whereas many young women without education have been employed in the service sector, as different low-paid service jobs have increased (e.g. Hiilamo & Aaltonen 2020; Swart, Holte, Hiilamo 2022). These structural changes have had an impact on the labour markets in Päijät-Häme and Eastern Uusimaa, the regions from which the Finnish young people were recruited for the SocEntYouth project.

These structural changes are at least partly connected to other changes in work and working life, the most important of which are technologisation and digitalisation of work and the drastic increase of knowledge work, which has changed the nature of work and occupations. These transformations have also changed the nature of education, as the growing need for knowledge in work has posed the challenge and pressure to make changes to the educational degrees for them to better correspond to the current qualifications, which are typical in white-collar professional work. This development

has had an influence on the positions of young people as learners, which can ultimately lead to the polarisation of the labour market. (E.g. Hiilamo & Aaltonen 2020.)

As the situation of young people in the labour market is polarised in European Union member states due to the aforementioned structural reasons, there is a strong need to consider other opportunities to gain a livelihood while promoting an attitudinal change regarding working life, sufficient income, and the meaning of life in general. According to youth researchers, it is due to this social change that different forms of self-employment have become worthwhile for young people to contemplate (e.g. Furlong & Cartmel 2007).

In Latvia, the unemployment rate of young people aged 15-24 in 2024 was 13.6 % and has risen 1.3 percentage points from the year 2023. The unemployment rate was 21.2 % and much higher among young persons categorised as having no formal education in 2023, but it has lowered by 2.2 percentage points by the year 2024, as the rate was then 19%. The average unemployment rate was 6.6 % of the labour force in Latvia in 2023, and in a year, the increase was 0.62 percentage points. (Oficiālās Statistikas Portāls, Employment rate, unemployment rate, part-time employment by education, age and sex group per cent 2021-2024). However, in the capital Riga, the unemployment rate of persons in that age cohort was 5.6 % in total in 2023, so the difference is big between the

capital and other parts of Latvia (Oficiālās Statistikas Portāls, Activity Rate, employment rate and unemployment rate by gender and age groups in regions, state cities and municipalities at the beginning of the year 2021-2023).

According to the statistics, the average unemployment rate appears to be higher in Finland than in Latvia. However, in comparison with the average unemployment rate in both countries, the youth unemployment rate seems to be higher in Latvia than in Finland. In light of the statistics, it is also evident that capital areas and larger cities offer more employment opportunities for young people. In international studies on youth mobility, it has been argued that as the willingness of young people to move from rural regions to the cities is strong for them to find better opportunities, it decreases the opportunities in the rural regions correspondingly. Mobility away from the countryside and smaller cities diminishes the service provision in these regions, thereby affecting the quality of life. The consequences of this development are drastic, especially for those young people who would want to stay in their home regions. (e.g. Penttinen 2016; see also Eriksson & Ronkainen 2016; Moisala & Saari 2025.)

In summary, the concerns about young people, particularly those without formal higher education, are understandable when considering the statistical data on youth unemployment in both Finland and Latvia, which reflects the general situation of young people in

the EU. Especially in disadvantaged areas, more employment solutions are needed.

The SocEntYouth project was targeted at those having fewer opportunities, with no formal higher education or lower educational degrees, and/or living outside the capital area. Enhancing the skills of young people for self-employment by ideating and planning to start a social enterprise has been the focus of the project. It would help young people with more knowledge and ideas for self-employment and thus provide them with better prospects. The project activity thus contributes to sustainable livelihoods and economies in disadvantaged areas and regions in which the sources of economic well-being have decreased.

According to the policy papers and recommendations made, for example, by the European Youth Forum in 2011, aligned with the EU action plan for the social economy of that year, support in the self-employment of young people by increasing their entrepreneurial skills would be one noteworthy solution. It would enhance their employment opportunities in disadvantaged areas and simultaneously create sustainable livelihoods that contribute to the common good and thus promote community wellbeing. (Position paper on youth entrepreneurship 2011; see also Social Economy Action Plan 2021, Read 8.2.2025.) Additionally, it has been stated to be important to create and strengthen social and immaterial economies to reduce the

dependence on natural resources to help sustain the carrying capacity of the globe. For example, social entrepreneurship would then contribute to these endeavours, as well.

2. Social enterprise as a form of entrepreneurship in Finland and Latvia

According to scholars, there is no generally accepted or universal definition for social entrepreneurship, although it is seen to be conceptually clear in terms of what it involves (e.g. Millere et al. 2023). In the broadest sense, social enterprise is defined, for example, as a set of innovative activities addressed to make a change in the social system to benefit the larger community (e.g. Revko 2017). Social enterprise seeks financial profit, but it must allocate most of the profit to benefit the community. Social entrepreneurship, therefore, involves the production of goods or services to solve a social problem and to benefit society rather than increasing the profits of the business owners (Millere et al. 2023).

For example, if a person sets up a social enterprise to help the elderly have meaningful, accessible creative activities, the entrepreneur must allocate most of the profit, for instance, to developing accessible activities for the elderly to be used for free. For the enterprise to gain financial profit, the basic activities usually entail selling a product or a service to a larger clientele.

Therefore, crucial in social entrepreneurship is the social worth or value of the activity. For example, work integration is a common social aim, which means helping people who have difficulties in accessing the labour market, such as persons with disabilities, migrants or former prisoners, by hiring them to work in the enterprise. Their employment is usually financed by the activity itself, for example, by selling the product manufactured in the enterprise. The basic societal function of the enterprise is then the wider impact on the wellbeing of the community, as the basic idea is to help the disadvantaged.

The initiator of the idea of social business was Bangladeshi Muhammed Yunus, who started with the allowance of micro-credits to local farmers in 1983, to help them with their livelihood. Nowadays, his legacy is preserved in a global hub of social business, the Yunus Centre in Dhaka, Bangladesh. Principles of social business were defined by Yunus as follows (2009): 1) The goal is not to make the most money, but to prevent poverty or solve a social problem; 2) financial and economic sustainability is important for the enterprise; 3) investors get back only their investment without interest; 4) the company's profit is invested in the development of the company; 5) responsibility towards environment must be observed; 6) the workforce is provided with wages appropriate to the labour market and good working conditions; 7) those involved must do their work with joy. (Seven Principles of Social Business 2009).

In Finland, there are currently approximately 3,000 social enterprises, employing approximately 60,000 people. Most of the enterprises function in the field of social and health services, and other basic fields are education, recycling of materials and culture production. The largest amusement park in the country, Linnanmäki, based in the capital Helsinki, is the most well-known of Finnish social enterprises, and it's owned by the Children's Day Foundation.

There is no separate legislation for social enterprises in Finland, and juridically, they are not distinguished from other enterprises. Partly due to this, there is no such support provided for social enterprises by the state, as in Latvia, such as tax benefits, for example. According to research, the reasons for it are based on the firm development of the welfare state from the 1960s onwards and strongly developed and institutionalised wellbeing services. In a cultural sense, it has influenced the social values and normative understanding that social problems should be solved by the state and the welfare institutions and services, for which the income tax is allocated to a large extent. (e.g. Kostilainen 2019.) Social values based on the presumption that distributing welfare should be basically the responsibility of the state influence young people as well, and their unwillingness to become entrepreneurs in the fields relevant to social enterprises (Rantanen & Toikko 2013).

The state of Finland, nevertheless, provides support for social enterprises by maintaining the Expertise Centre of Social Entrepreneurship in Finland (YYO), which is partly funded by the European Social Fund. The centre promotes research and development of social entrepreneurship, and provides expert services, for instance, in promoting education and training in the field.

Despite the different types of support provided in the two countries, it has been argued in national research that there is no clear public understanding either in Finland (Kostilainen 2019) or Latvia (Vevere et al. 2021) about the goals of social entrepreneurship. In Latvia, the Social Enterprise Law was adopted in 2018, and the status of social entrepreneurship in the Latvian business environment is defined in it. The adoption of the law facilitated the fast development of social entrepreneurship in Latvia, and many new enterprises have been established in the country in recent years, the number of which moves between 200 and 300. According to the statistics from the Statistical Data of the Social Enterprises 2023, most of the social enterprises in Latvia deal with work integration (23% of the enterprises), education (21%) and sport, health promotion and medicine (19%). More than half of the social enterprises are based in the Riga region. According to a recent study, they are regionally very unevenly distributed, especially if the need to reduce the social risks of Latvian

citizens living in different regions is taken into account. (Millere et al. 2023.)

Many enterprises have voluntarily joined the Social Entrepreneurship Association of Latvia, established to safeguard their interests and goals at the local and national levels. (Velvere et al. 2021). Under the social enterprise law, there are demands specified for the enterprises to be qualified as “social”, and the law also stipulates the requirement to measure the social impact of the enterprise. Latvian social entrepreneurs must submit an annual activity report to the government, and it should include information on providing and measuring the social impact of the enterprise and provide evidence that proves the achieved social impact, such as external evaluations and stories on the experiences of the beneficiaries. (Millere et al. 2023.)

The state of Latvia supports social enterprises with tax benefits, such as the real estate tax benefits granted by the municipalities, and reductions in the corporate income tax base for certain groups of expenses which are not related to economic activity. The state also provides other types of support for social enterprises, such as giving them the right to engage volunteers for activities that are not related to the administration or accounting of the enterprise. (Ibid.)

In sum, the status of social enterprises is clearly defined in the Latvian legislation. Supported by the state, they are accountable for their functioning and

the social impact of their activities. In Finland, social entrepreneurship has no defined status in the legislation, and social enterprises do not receive support from the state to the extent of Latvia. These different premises regarding the status of social enterprises have also influenced the implementation of the project and the knowledge of the young people recruited for it.

3. Attitudes towards entrepreneurship among youth in Finland and Latvia

Despite the growing fields of entrepreneurship, only a little more than one-fourth of the Finnish youth would be interested in setting up their own enterprise, as evidenced by the latest Flash Eurobarometer (2023). According to a few Finnish studies, the willingness of Finnish people to start an enterprise has been lower than the average in the European Union for decades (Rantanen & Toikko 2013). According to a survey in which the attitudes towards working life and entrepreneurship were studied in 2013 among young people aged 12-29 (N=1600 appr.) living in Eastern Finland, there have been significant gender differences in the attitudes influencing the willingness to start with entrepreneurship in the future. Among young men, the reasons for considering the option were most often the possibilities to become prosperous and succeed, and to gain influence and respect. Among women, the most influential potential reasons for taking up entrepreneurship in the

future were the opportunities to realise one's own values and dreams. (Eero-la-Ockenström 2013.)

Vice versa, the most crucial reasons for the unwillingness to take up entrepreneurship were the financial risks with both genders, but significantly more often with women (52 % of the respondents) than men (38% of the respondents). Mental load and stress caused by the responsibility were the most often reported reasons among young women for not considering taking up entrepreneurship in the future. (Ibid.)

According to the national Finnish Youth Barometer conducted in 2019, interest in becoming an entrepreneur has risen over the past decade among young people aged 15-29 years. 59 % of the interviewees (N=1907 appr.) were interested in experimenting with entrepreneurship at some point in their lives. (Haikkola & Myllyniemi 2019.) Technology, digitalisation and different creative opportunities were the basic fields raising enthusiasm for entrepreneurship among young people at a national level, and their self-employment was related mostly to these fields (Berg & Ylöstalo 2019). Sixty interviewees were entrepreneurs themselves, and many of them worked in traditional fields, such as agriculture. More than half of all interviewees felt that the current educational system in Finland did not provide sufficient knowledge on entrepreneurship, and that provision of knowledge should be increased at all educational levels.

More than half of the interviewees also felt that they hadn't had enough encouragement for entrepreneurship in their homes. (Haikkola & Myllyniemi 2019; Mikkilä 2019.)

In Latvia and other Baltic countries, rates of young people interested in entrepreneurship are higher, as evidenced by the latest Flash Eurobarometer (2023) and Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (2025). One reason for the very different level of interest in entrepreneurship in Latvia, as well as in other Baltic countries, can be the lower income level and high rate of financial inequality, which fosters the imagination for entrepreneurship to be a viable option to make a living (see Pathak & Muralidharan 2018). In the Nordic countries, financial inequality is lower, and public welfare and strong welfare institutions and services mitigate the difficulties of finding employment (ibid.; Lindberg & Kostilainen 2021). Another reason for young people's stronger enthusiasm to start entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship in contemporary Latvia is the support by the state, and the increase of entrepreneurship education at all educational levels in recent years (Vevere et al. 2021).

Thus, in light of research, there are differences between Finland and Latvia when it comes to the attitudes towards entrepreneurship among young people, and the reflections of these factors will be scrutinised, considering those who participated in the SocEntYouth project.

PART 2

**Implementation of the Social
Business Academy training
programme**

This part of the report deals with the implementation and the course of the training programme. It involves a description of the basic content of the training, its organisation, and forms of teaching. In this part, the outcomes of the project are presented first by introducing the basic outcomes of the internal mid-term evaluation report, based on the experiences of the first training cycle completed by 33 Finnish and Latvian young people. Thereafter, the outcomes of the total three training cycles are presented, based on the description of the quantitative and qualitative feedback data gained from the young people participating in the training.

1. Planning and organisation of the training

This section entails descriptions of planning and designing processes of the training materials, and practical implementation of the first training cycle, which functioned as the pilot of the training programme of social entrepreneurship for both young people between 18 and 25 years of age, and people living in Europe.

Planning the training materials and the training programme

Planning of the training started in June 2023. The training was named “Social Business Academy”, for it to be more easily advertised to recruit the participants, rather than with the original

project name. At first, the planning included the examination of the training materials that were first designed by the Latvian association Reach for Change to pilot the educational programme in African countries, such as Ghana and Ethiopia, and customising them to be piloted in this project in Europe and among young people. The training materials were thought to serve as theoretical content and useful practical tips in order for young people to learn the core activities and functions of a social enterprise. By proceeding step by step with the theoretical content and doing practical tasks relating to these theoretical steps, it was thought to help the trainees develop ideas for social businesses according to their own interests.

It was realised that much more needed to be adapted than initially thought for the training materials to fit the new target audience. More illustrative examples and practical toolkits for learning the theoretical issues were added to the original materials, as well as examples derived from actual functioning social enterprises, so that the training was developed to better fit the needs of young people.

The improved design of the materials for Social Business Academy included a theoretical basis and practical advice to define such social problems that could be solved by social business activity, define a value base for the enterprise, define the clientele or beneficiaries of the enterprise, define

the financial base of the activity, and define the core activities of the enterprise. Illustrative toolkits, such as Problem Tree to define a social problem and its root causes, and Business Model Canvas to help develop a business idea, were planned to be used in the training for the participants to adopt the theoretical knowledge more easily and to contemplate it practically. These separate themes or components in the process of setting up an enterprise formed the basis of the Social Business Academy training curriculum, and the training content were planned to be adjusted into a fixed set of schedules with the same duration to teach each component.

The themes were connected with different ideation tasks, so that the participants would be able to start brainstorming with their own potential enterprises. These practical ideation tasks were considered important for diverse young people, so that the training would be accessible to all participants regardless of their abilities to adopt new knowledge on issues unfamiliar beforehand.

These training materials entailed a lot of information, but the materials entailing more specific theoretical knowledge were decided to be left as additional learning material for those participants who wanted to learn the issues more in-depth than the basic training would provide. Online toolkit materials (The Reach for Change platform) were decided to be left at the

mentoring stage to be implemented after the basic training, intended for those participants who would want to continue to develop their business ideas with a mentor.

The training materials were drafted in English by adapting the training for youth, especially. The materials were reviewed by the Finnish partner DILA and the Latvian partner Creative Ideas, who were responsible for the practical training. At this stage, the partners were able to suggest changes in the materials. After these suggestions were agreed upon, the materials were translated into Latvian and Finnish by external translators. Thereafter, the translations were checked by the project staff, and if needed, corrections were made in accordance with the national terminology related to entrepreneurship.

After the preparation phase, four (4) training sessions for trainers were arranged so that the trainers in both countries were able to get acquainted with the training materials beforehand. The first session was a 2-day training taking place in Riga, Latvia, and it was followed by three (3) training sessions arranged online. At this stage, the trainers could ask questions regarding the use of the materials in practical training. Unfortunately, some of the trainers were not able to participate in these training sessions because of conflicting schedules. The project staff, training designers and trainers had many discussions during these

sessions, and some worries were expressed concerning young people as the participants of the training programme, particularly young people with learning difficulties. The worries related to the facilitation, and whether it is sufficient for the young people to understand the theoretical content of the materials.

The implementation of the training program and the schedules were planned in accordance with the order of the original training materials. The implementation was planned by the project staff in DILA and Creative Ideas for the training to be implemented in parallel in both countries. Initially, the training was planned to be implemented in two (2) separate cycles so that both cycles would involve 120 participants altogether. However, during the course of the project, it turned out to be difficult to involve all intended participants in the two training cycles, and it was decided later that a third training cycle would be added to the project programme.

The training in each training cycle was agreed to involve three (3) complementary parts. The first part (1) was called Bootcamp training, including a 2-day onsite training (Bootcamp Onsite) for Finnish and Latvian young people, parallel in both countries. Onsite training was followed by online training sessions in both Finland and Latvia in parallel during the four following weeks (Bootcamp Online). The last session of the online training 'the Pitch Day' in which the participants could present

their business ideas, was agreed to be conducted as a joint session for the trainees of both countries and implemented in the English language.

The second (2) part of the training, Leadership Camp, was planned to be implemented as a 3-day onsite joint session, also serving as an opportunity for the young people from Finland and Latvia to meet and get acquainted. The purpose of Leadership Camp was to help the young people develop their leadership skills and soft skills and train them to develop entrepreneurial mindsets. The third (3) part of the training, the Innovation Lab, was planned to be a voluntary one-on-one mentoring program arranged in parallel in both countries for those participants who were willing to continue to develop their business ideas after the basic training was completed. The participants in the Innovation Lab were to gain access to the digital platform with online toolkits.

Recruiting the young people

To attract and recruit participants for the training, multiple approaches were employed in parallel. The recruitment campaign for cycle 1 was started in September 2023 and concluded in January 2024. The cycle 2 recruitment campaign was carried out between August and October of 2024. The final campaign for cycle 3 took place between December 2024 and February 2025.

Targeted social media campaigns were carried out in both Latvia and Finland, with organic content published on the social media pages of Reach for Change Latvia, Creative Ideas, and DILA. In addition, paid advertisements were used to extend the campaign's reach and engage a broader audience.

The first cycle (henceforth cycle 1) of the "Social Business Academy" training started in the autumn of 2023 by recruiting young adults to participate in the training. In Latvia, participants were recruited mostly by email and online announcements on social media. Also, phone calls were used to attract those young people who were personally known to the project staff. Discussions were held with several local youth workers and teachers, who helped in advertising the training. The recruited young people also spread the word on their social networks. In addition, in cycles 2 and 3, social media influencers were hired in both Latvia and Finland to help spread the word about this training among youth.

In Finland, the process was quite rapid after developing several means to recruit young people, such as visiting schools and local youth services, to reach potential participants. The social media campaign was generally more successful in Latvia, but for the second and third cycles, social media campaigns were successfully deployed in Finland, as well, and many Finnish participants were recruited with the help of social media posts and efficient marketing.

Latvian participants were recruited from Riga (11 participants), the outskirts of Riga (5 participants) and other regions in Latvia (49 participants). Finnish participants were recruited from the Lahti region (47 participants), other localities in the Päijät-Häme region (8 participants) and outside of the Päijät-Häme region (12 participants). In Finland, seven (7) participants had other than native Finnish origin. The ages of the participants ranged from 18 to 25 years, both in Finland and Latvia.

The socioeconomic and educational statuses of the participants varied in both countries. In Latvia, 31 persons were students, 32 persons didn't study, and 2 persons were involved in short term courses. 17 of the Latvian participants were employed. In Finland, 35 persons were students, 28 persons didn't study, 2 persons were involved in short term courses, and the status of one person was unknown.

The educational backgrounds of the participants were varied as well. Those 66 persons with student statuses were students mostly at the higher educational level, for example, at scientific or vocational universities. Some were students at vocational institutions. A few of them were still at upper secondary school. The number of those who didn't study had lower educational backgrounds, such as comprehensive school. The educational background was unknown of some of the participants with migrant statuses.

Bootcamp Onsite training

The training for the first cycle was held in February and March 2024, the second cycle in November and December 2024 and the third cycle in February and March 2025. In cycle 1, the Bootcamp training was implemented onsite in the city of Lahti in Finland and the city of Riga in Latvia. The Bootcamp onsite training in both countries involved 5-7 active hours of training each day. In Finland, the onsite days of cycle 1 involved approximately one active hour more per day than in Latvia.

During the Bootcamp onsite training in Finland, external presenters and trainers were recruited to train the participants, whereas in Latvia, the training was conducted by the staff of the association Creative Ideas. The training in both countries consisted of lectures based on the training materials. The lectures were followed by group work tasks, during which the participants developed their ideas for social businesses.

Finnish external trainers and lecturers were entrepreneurs, service designers and long-term experts and trainers of entrepreneurship. They gave presentations about the basic operations of starting an enterprise, planning a coherent business idea that is distinguishable from the currently functioning enterprises, financial planning, marketing, and client potential.

The crucial expertise on social entrepreneurship was presented by a trainer from the organisation of alliance and network of social enterprises in Finland (ARVO – the Finnish Association of Social Enterprises). That training consisted of presentations concerning the basic operations of a social enterprise, and the participants were given several group tasks relating to the different topics based on the original training materials. However, the Finnish trainers gave many examples of functioning social enterprises in Finnish scale and context, so that to a large extent, the training reflected Finnish entrepreneurial environments and conditions.

Importantly, the trainers supervised and supported the participants to develop their business ideas in groups. In each group, the first task was to define a social problem to be solved by certain entrepreneurial activities, according to which the group participants further developed a social business model. The training was focused on developing these business ideas with the help of the toolkits included in the training materials. The business models were developed by consistently following the original training materials. The groups worked with 1) defining a social problem to be solved by social business activity, 2) defining the value base of the enterprise, 3) defining the clientele or beneficiaries of the enterprise, 4) defining the financial base of the business activity, and 5) defining the core activities of the social enterprise. Bootcamp Onsite training was

concluded in Finland by pitching the business ideas of each group, and at this stage, they got feedback and advice from the trainers to develop the ideas further.

In Latvia, the original training materials were followed closely, and the training was adjusted according to the Latvian entrepreneurial environment. The trainer of the association Creative Ideas followed the training program in a similar way to the training in Finland, and after the theoretical lecture on each of the aforementioned topics, the training was focused on helping young people develop their business ideas. In Latvia as well, the Bootcamp Onsite was concluded by the pitching session of the participants to present their business ideas.

Bootcamp Online training

Online training started in training cycle 1, the next week after Bootcamp Onsite. Both in Finland and Latvia, there were 4-15 participants involved in the online training in each of the eight (8) sessions, two sessions per week. It was less than the number of those participants who attended the onsite training. In Finland, the online training consisted of presentations by external speakers, followed by training sessions and group work conducted by an external trainer. The trainers and lecturers in Finland were not the same persons in Bootcamp Online as those in Bootcamp Onsite.

The online sessions in Finland began with a presentation of a young entrepreneur, who talked about their background and personal profile as an entrepreneur lasting for 20 minutes. The rest of the two-hour session was conducted by a young entrepreneur and trainer, whose expertise lies mainly in traditional entrepreneurship. The trainer based the teaching mostly on the original training materials of the SocEntYouth project. The participants were encouraged to further develop their business ideas, and these ideas were assessed by the trainer during the concluding session of the online training.

In Finland, the participants also had the opportunity to pitch their business ideas to a Finnish financial investor of enterprises, who provided the participants with advice on developing their business plans. The examples and advice given by the financial investor were from the field of traditional entrepreneurship.

In Latvia, the online training in the first cycle consisted of 40-minute lectures, during which the theoretical content were presented thoroughly, and 20-minute group work based on this training. The original plan was to implement two-hour training sessions. The online training in Latvia was conducted by trainers from Creative Ideas. The last session of Bootcamp Online was organised in English, as it was a joint session of both countries. The joint session was a pitching session,

in which one representative of each group presented the business idea developed in the group.

Already during the online Bootcamp training, the mentoring process began with those who wanted to advance their ideas. The mentoring process was planned to function through discussions between the mentor and the mentee. It was planned that with the mentor's support, the young person could further develop the business idea, even to the phase of starting the business. The discussions were planned to handle the mentee's perceptions of the benefits of the knowledge of social entrepreneurship that was provided in the training, the individual progress of the mentee, as well as the possible difficulties and worries regarding the training program. External experts were recruited as mentors in Finland, such as experienced entrepreneurs, and a few of the trainers who served as external trainers in the basic training. External experts, such as experienced entrepreneurs, were used as mentors as well in Latvia.

Leadership Camp

The third part of the training program in cycle 1 was Leadership Camp, organised onsite in Riga, Latvia and Tallinn, Estonia during cycles 2 and 3. Leadership Camp was a joint event for the participants of both countries, and it was conducted in English. In Riga, the training focused on helping the participants develop their leadership skills, as

well as developing their entrepreneurial thinking and mindset. The training in Riga consisted of external presentations from Finland and Latvia, and the group work that was part of the training of a few of the presenters. These external trainers and presenters are experts in the entrepreneurial field and experienced trainers. Finnish experts conducted their presentations online, and the Latvians presented onsite.

The first part of Leadership Camp in Riga in cycle 1 dealt with leadership skills in conducting an enterprise. The trainers gave the participants group tasks in which they could contemplate and discuss what good leadership is, and how to develop the mindset relating to good leadership. After training in leadership skills, attention was given to developing thinking skills for the ideation of business ideas. This part of the training was the responsibility of external expert associations, enterprises and hubs providing training for organisations for ideation and critical thinking. The trainers provided by these enterprises gave the participants group tasks to develop their critical and creative thinking skills and skills of using imagination for the ideation of business ideas.

Leadership Camp in Riga was the conclusion of the basic training of the Social Business Academy in cycle 1. During the concluding session, the participant certificates were handed out to the participants, and a separate feedback conversation was arranged

in order for the young people to give any feedback concerning the training.

Innovation Lab

After the Leadership Camp and being awarded a certificate for participation, most young people concluded their training. However, 8 (eight) participants of the Social Business Academy altogether started in the Innovation Lab, a mentoring programme for those who wanted to proceed further with their ideas, and even to start an enterprise with the help of an individual mentor.

During the mentors' meetings (3-5 times for each mentee), the mentees could develop the same ideas for social enterprises which they developed during the basic training, or they could innovate new ideas. The participants could utilise the knowledge gained from the basic training very freely to develop their own business ideas. Most mentees preferred ideas that could contribute to their artistic endeavours and interests, such as developing their own crocheting or clothing designs and selling them in official marketplaces.

The mentors, both in Finland and Latvia, are experienced entrepreneurs, and they gave advice and support to their mentees to help them build an individual entrepreneurial path. The participants still had access to advanced online training materials, which were provided to all participants during the

basic training. During cycle 1 in Finland, four (4) trainees participated as mentees in the Innovation Lab. One person proceeded with planning her own marketing strategy and was prepared to start an enterprise. Most Finnish mentees finished the Innovation Lab after receiving individual support in planning and designing their own product, and advice on planning the financial structure for their business idea.

During the first training cycle in Latvia, four (4) mentees joined the Innovation Lab. All benefited from the mentors' advice in some way, and one person developed an idea for an art workshop for persons with disabilities and felt ready to put the idea into practice.

Feedback on the training program

Participant feedback was collected by a staff member serving as an evaluator in the SocEntYouth project, who works as a researcher at the Juvenia Centre of Youth Research and Development based in South-Eastern Finland University of Applied Sciences. Tools to collect participant feedback on the training were planned and designed in the winter of 2024 before the training cycle 1. E-surveys were considered to work best for Bootcamp training with the participants in both Finland and Latvia, and the feedback questionnaires were designed with the Webropol online survey tool. In addition to the collection of feedback on the training, it was contemplated among the

project staff that a self-evaluation tool to measure the increase of knowledge on social entrepreneurship and the improvement of entrepreneurial skills was an appropriate way to map out and test the functioning of the planned training program.

E-surveys were then drafted for 1) self-assessment of the young people participating in the programme, considering their knowledge of social entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship in general, and such personal skills that support entrepreneurial mindset (see appendix n:o 1), and 2) participant feedback concerning the training of Bootcamp onsite and online (see appendixes n:o 2-3). Self-assessment was planned to be implemented both before and after the training, so that the actual increase in the knowledge and skills of the trainees could be measured by comparing the responses to the questionnaires sent before and after the training.

The e-surveys for participant feedback were designed by defining a series of statements considering the training, and the responses were measured quantitatively using a Likert scale matrix, in which the respondents could choose the response option that best suited their opinion. Also, a possibility for open feedback was given at the end of the e-questionnaire. The self-assessment questionnaires were designed in a similar way by using statements describing the knowledge and skills in social entrepreneurship

and its core functions, and the respondents were able to choose the option in a Likert scale matrix, which they assumed to best correspond to their level of knowledge.

During the training cycle 1, the participants responded to the feedback questionnaires shortly after the training sessions were concluded. The self-assessment survey measuring the level of their knowledge and skills gathered higher response rates both before and after the training than the feedback survey. Partly, this was a consequence of the fact that they were advised to respond to the self-assessment survey during the onsite training, both before and after the training, so that the staff could monitor the participants as they filled in the surveys.

During training cycle 1, in both Finland and Latvia, the response rate was high concerning the training in Bootcamp Onsite and low concerning the Bootcamp Online. During cycle 1, feedback was collected separately concerning the online training. The lower response rates concerning the online training were probably due to the inability of staff to encourage the participants to respond, so many participants missed the opportunity to give feedback. However, the rate of attendance was lower in online training, which has affected the result accordingly. The need to fill in several questionnaires during the whole training process might also have been confusing and exhausting to the participants.

Additionally, oral feedback was collected both spontaneously by discussing with the participants informally during the breaks, for example, and in the feedback conversation during the concluding session in the Leadership Camp joint event. The feedback conversation was led by the staff, during which the opinions of the participants were mapped out about the sufficiency of knowledge of social entrepreneurship provided in the training and organisation of the training program of both Bootcamp and Leadership Camp. The participants were able to express freely their general impressions of the training program and give suggestions to improve it. The conversation was vivid, and the basic topics were summed up by the staff writing them down.

In addition to the feedback discussions, three (3) feedback interviews were conducted and recorded with the interviewees' consent in order to get more in-depth knowledge of the impressions of the participants. 4 (four) persons were interviewed in total, as two participants were interviewed together. Interviews of the Finnish participants were conducted in the Finnish language, and Latvian participants in English.

Feedback was collected as well from external trainers and mentors regarding the knowledge base of entrepreneurship provided in the training, and the organisation of the programme. Their impressions regarding the engagement of the young people were also collected.

In addition to these means of collecting feedback on the training, observation data was collected by closely following the run of the training sessions, and these observations were written down. However, the observation method could only be applied during the Finnish training and the joint events conducted in English, as the staff member responsible for the evaluation process is Finnish and unfamiliar with the Latvian language.

2. Results of the participant feedback on the training cycle 1 and the basic conclusions in the mid-term evaluation phase

A mid-term evaluation was conducted for internal purposes for the SocEn-Youth project. Internal evaluation after the first training cycle was considered necessary for the staff to utilise the participant feedback to improve the functionality of the training programme for the second and third training cycles.

The data for the mid-term evaluation was collected during the Bootcamp and Leadership Camp training, by e-questionnaires for self-assessment of knowledge and skills, and feedback on the training. In addition to this, feedback conversations were organised during the on-site joint events. As the Finnish evaluator is unfamiliar with the Latvian language, the oral feedback concerning Bootcamp Onsite training in Latvia was collected by the trainer at

Creative Ideas, who then gave summaries of the conversations with the Latvian participants. The data for the mid-term evaluation was collected as well by observing the training sessions in Bootcamp Onsite in Finland and the Leadership Camp joint event arranged in Riga in March 2024.

The basic impressions provided by the participant feedback data were related to the generally positive views of the trainees involved in the training cycle 1, regarding the knowledge provided in the training, the forms and quality of teaching, the sufficiency of knowledge provided on social entrepreneurship and the possibility to create their own ideas for enterprises. The face-to-face joint event (Leadership Camp) was considered very useful and fun, and many highlighted the importance of transnational collaboration.

According to the feedback provided in e-surveys, the training was considered mostly useful in increasing knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, and the training was felt to have been implemented very well. However, the e-survey responses given by the Latvian participants were more positive than those given by the Finns. Given this result, the implementation of the training in Finland was planned to be organised differently in a few crucial respects for the training cycle 2. The survey responses indicate, to some extent, that the more detailed and profound the training has been in certain fields, for

example, when using specific, sophisticated methods to plan a business idea, the more difficulties there presumably have been in understanding the teaching.

The teaching was emphasised on the general principles of starting an enterprise and entrepreneurship on the first day in Finland. Being left to the afternoon hours, there was apparently a lack of energy to properly learn the basic principles of social entrepreneurship. In addition to these timing troubles, there were some problematic issues regarding the expertise of the trainers; only one of the three external trainers had social entrepreneurship as the basic field of expertise, which might have affected the different learning outcomes from those of the Latvian participants. Most groups developed and presented very traditional business ideas without elements that would have added social value or benefit to their business models, or in other ways to indicate their worth as a social enterprise.

Some problems were related to the organisation of the training. As the trainees worked in groups, it was difficult to recognise such participants, who would have benefited from additional support to understand the teaching. As the trainees were encouraged to develop only one business idea per group, the risk of being a passive participant was higher than in a situation in which an individual participant is allowed to develop an idea. It is possible that

the practice of one idea per group has raised the risk of not learning. It was affirmed by the e-survey responses that not all participants felt they had learned the taught content.

that the difficulty level of teaching corresponded to the level of knowledge of those older participants, who had background education in entrepreneurship.

The inclusion of students with different educational backgrounds may have discouraged those who would have needed additional support. It was verbalised, for example, in the open question section of the e-survey by one Finnish participant, who had noticed the uneven situation and argued

For example, the question posed in the e-survey indicating that the training met one's personal needs and aims of learning, showed Latvians to have been more content with their training, whereas 38% of the Finns were discontent in that respect (37 respondents altogether, see table no. 1):

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate what you think of the following statements (1 = agree; 2 = somewhat agree; 3 = don't know; 4 = somewhat disagree; 5 = disagree)

Table 1: Feedback on Bootcamp Onsite of the first training cycle by participants in Finland and Latvia: The teaching corresponded to my goals and learning needs.

However, as indicated in table 1, there were more of those among the Finnish participants (black bars) who agreed with the proposition “The training met my personal needs and aims for learning” (31%), whereas the Latvians (orange bars) mostly somewhat agreed (46%).

Some differences between the Latvians and the Finns were striking, concerning the elements of social entrepreneurship. For example, 87% of the Latvians felt they had learnt the

difference between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, whereas only 46% of the Finns felt so. A difference to a similar extent between Latvians and Finns appeared in the responses to the question of whether they had learnt the basic principles of the goals and operations of a social enterprise (see table 2). Over a third of the Finnish respondents (black bars) also felt they didn’t learn to create a business model, whereas most of the Latvians (orange bars) felt they did.

On a scale of 1 to 5, rate what you think of the following statements (1=I agree; 2=I somewhat agree; 3=I don’t know; 4=I somewhat disagree; 5=I disagree):

Table 2: Feedback on Bootcamp Onsite training, cycle 1, participants in Finland and Latvia: I learnt the basic principles of the goals and operations of a social enterprise.

One reason for the Finns to give more negative responses might have been the large proportion of teaching that was concentrated on the basic

elements of traditional entrepreneurship during the Bootcamp, so the basics of social entrepreneurship were left with a lesser understanding. During

the Bootcamp onsite training in Finland, the participants were advised to create their own business models, but many wanted to create a traditional business idea. Despite that, all business ideas were equally encouraged to be developed further, even though many participants remained in a traditional business model. In sum, as the teaching was concentrated in most parts of traditional entrepreneurship, it reflected straightforwardly on the ability of the participants to grasp the core values and principles of social entrepreneurship, which was the aim of the training program.

Another reason may be that some participants had difficulties understanding the taught content. Educational backgrounds varied significantly among the participants, and a few of them did not have a secondary education to support this training. The participants would have benefited from additional support, which was not often asked for and, therefore, not given. As the participants worked mostly in groups, the need for individual, additional support remained unnoticed by the trainers.

In the section of the participant feedback e-survey concerning the practical functionality of the training to plan a social business, the responses indicated that the Latvians felt it again more positively than the Finnish, but not as strikingly as with the section on learning the basic elements of social entrepreneurship. Approximately 64% of Latvian and 48% of Finnish respondents were

positive in this section and felt that the training gave sufficient knowledge and tools for planning a social enterprise. However, these figures also reveal that almost half of the participants in both countries did not feel they had gained enough knowledge to start their own enterprise.

3. Adjustments and changes for cycles 2 and 3 according to the participant feedback and general experiences from cycle 1

As part of the assessment following the first cycle pilot implementation, there were areas for improvement identified in both the content and organisation of the training in the mid-term evaluation conducted after cycle 1. Based on feedback collected from participants, project partners, and mentors, a revised training design was developed and proposed by Reach for Change and shared with the partners for review. Following this consultation, an updated version of the program structure and training materials was finalised.

The revised program was intended to run over five consecutive weekends. According to the design, it would begin with two days of in-person training (~12 contact hours, reduced from ~16) focused on foundational topics such as introductions to social entrepreneurship, ideation workshops, and team formation. This would be followed by three weeks (previously

four) of online engagement, with one 1.5-hour session and one 2-hour workshop per week, totalling ~10.5 hours (down from ~16). A key design change was the separation of theory-based sessions from practical workshops, replacing the previous format of eight mixed sessions. This was intended to improve participants' ability to absorb and apply concepts effectively.

Another new element in the revised design was the introduction of Milestones - structured checkpoints designed to track the progress of participants. At each milestone, teams formed by the young people were expected to submit practical outputs such as creating their own versions of a Problem Tree, in which a particular social problem and its root causes are defined, a Business Model Canvas based on their business ideas, or implement a video pitch. These were to be stored in shared folders, allowing mentors to provide timely, targeted feedback. Dedicated mentoring sessions were intended to support participants in processing this feedback and aligning their next steps.

Not all elements of the revised design were implemented as planned by the project partners. Training was conducted on weekdays instead of weekends; the milestone structure in combination with mentoring sessions was not utilised as mentors were not assigned to each group as intended.

After the first cycle was completed, it was noticed that some things needed

to be changed to improve the organisation of the training as well. Online training didn't seem to be tempting for young people to participate, and there were only 4-14 of the total 35-45 participants involved in each of the four two-hour training periods. For cycle 2, the number of online sessions was reduced from eight to six in both countries, and the times were adjusted to the expressed preferences of the young people. However, this change was not fruitful either, as the number of participants attending was even lower during the second cycle.

As the youth attending the second cycle hoped for more transnational interaction in general, the online training of cycle 3 was arranged differently. Instead of remaining in separate national groups, for half of the workshops, the participants were united from both countries in the same online space, and the training was conducted in English. This arrangement also had the advantage that the attendants could communicate in English already before the onsite joint event, the Leadership Camp. Furthermore, in cycle 3 the online workshops were organised on the weekend, Saturday morning, according to the suggestions of the participants of cycle 2. However, despite unifying the participants from both countries and adjusting the time of the workshops, the participant rates of online training were also lower in training cycle 3 than Bootcamp Onsite training. Despite that, they were higher than in cycle 2, compared to the total

number of participants, which was lower in cycle 3.

For cycle 1, more time was added for online group work in Latvia, and the workshops lasted up to 1 h 20 min, due to the feedback of some students saying that 20 minutes was insufficient to develop ideas in groups. During training cycle 2, a joint online session was again arranged to conclude the online training, during which the participants from both Finland and Latvia pitched their business ideas and had the opportunity to discuss the ideas with peers. Additionally, in cycle 3, a format of asynchronous workshops was introduced so that the participants could watch half of the workshops online at a time suitable for them, as none of the proposed times for online workshops worked for everyone.

In Finland, with training cycle 2, the online training was given by the young entrepreneur, but no other external speakers were involved in the second cycle. In cycle 3, the online training in Finland and Latvia was combined, and the teaching was given in English by a trainer working in the association Creative Ideas in Latvia, also a member of the project staff and experienced with business training.

Changes needed to be made also in the organisation and content of the onsite training. In Finland, the most crucial observation of cycle 1 was that some participants were sticking to ideas of traditional businesses rather than

developing ideas for social enterprises. Consequently, the contributions of the external experts were changed in a way that the emphasis was on social entrepreneurship. In addition to that, the experts recruited to train the young people adjusted their training to align with the changes made to the training content and materials by the project staff.

In light of the experiences of cycle 1, the collection of feedback as well needed to be changed for cycles 2 and 3. In the mid-term evaluation phase, it was seen that the response rates were extremely low in the feedback survey concerning online teaching. Simplification of the feedback questionnaires was considered necessary to gain higher response rates, and the feedback concerning Bootcamp Onsite and Online training was combined in one e-questionnaire (see appendix n:o 4).

Despite this change, the response rates in the surveys concerning the feedback on the training in cycle 2 were again lower than in self-assessment surveys. However, during training cycle 3 there was lack of time for the participants to fill in the self-assessment survey already during the joint session, so the response rate was low (responses of 4-8 persons) in both countries in the self-assessment surveys as well, despite the attempts to prompt the participants to respond.

Feedback conversation was arranged during Leadership Camp during cycle

2 as well. The intention was to arrange the feedback conversation session again during cycle 3, but as the pitching session took more time than expected, there was no opportunity for a joint session for feedback in Tallinn, and the oral feedback was collected during the travel back home among the participants of both Latvia and Finland.

4. Results of the participant feedback on the training cycles 2 and 3 and the general conclusions

Considering the training process, including all cycles in total, the overall experience of the young people participating in the Social Business Academy was positive. As the process of feedback collection varied in terms of the programme schedules, the response rates varied, as well. For example, as there was no time to arrange the

feedback conversation session during the third cycle Leadership Camp, it, unfortunately, resulted in lower response rates to both e-surveys (post-training self-assessment survey and feedback survey), as the participants were unable to fill them in already during the joint session.

However, despite the low response rates to e-surveys during training cycle 3, the general outcomes of both self-assessment and feedback were positive. All participants of the Social Business Academy were generally content with the training, both the provided theoretical and practical knowledge, and the practical organisation. For comparison, below are presented the self-assessment survey responses of Finnish participants regarding the adopted knowledge of social entrepreneurship during cycle 2, and the Latvian participants during cycle 3 (see tables 3 and 4).

Rate your level of knowledge on a scale of 1 to 5 in the following areas (1 = little or no knowledge; 2 = some knowledge, 3 = mediocre knowledge; 4 = good knowledge; 5 = excellent knowledge):

Number of respondents: 15

	1	2	3	4	5	Average	Median
Entrepreneurship	0,0%	0,0%	13,4%	73,3%	13,3%	4,0	4,0
Social entrepreneurship	0,0%	20,0%	20,0%	40,0%	20,0%	3,6	4,0
Differences between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship	0,0%	0,0%	20,0%	40,0%	40,0%	4,2	4,0
Typical clientele of a social enterprise	6,7%	0,0%	46,7%	33,3%	13,3%	3,5	3,0
Understanding and defining social problems	0,0%	13,3%	13,3%	53,4%	20,0%	3,8	4,0
Understanding and developing ways to solve social problems	0,0%	6,7%	33,3%	60,0%	0,0%	3,5	4,0
The value or benefit of a social enterprise	0,0%	6,7%	26,7%	46,6%	20,0%	3,8	4,0
Business model and its components	0,0%	6,7%	26,7%	46,6%	20,0%	3,8	4,0
Altogether	0,8%	6,7%	25,0%	49,2%	18,3%	3,8	4,0

Table 3: Self-assessment of Finnish participants on their level of knowledge in social entrepreneurship after training on cycle 2.

The table shows that the median response of Finnish participants was “good knowledge” in all components, except the component of “typical clientele of a social enterprise”, in which they were more negative on average in their knowledge. Median was the same in Latvian responses during cycle 3, although the responses were

more positive in several components than those of the Finnish participants. It shows that the subjective impressions of Latvians on their own level of knowledge after participating in the training programme have been more positive than those of Finns, who have been slightly more moderate in their responses.

Rate your level of knowledge on a scale of 1 to 5 in the following areas (1 = little or no knowledge; 2 = some knowledge, 3 = mediocre knowledge; 4 = good knowledge; 5 = excellent knowledge):

Number of respondents: 8

	1	2	3	4	5	Average	Median
Business and companies	0,0%	0,0%	12,5%	75,0%	12,5%	4,0	4,0
Social entrepreneurship	0,0%	0,0%	25,0%	62,5%	12,5%	3,9	4,0
The difference between traditional entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	37,5%	62,5%	4,6	5,0
Clients in social entrepreneurship	0,0%	0,0%	12,5%	50,0%	37,5%	4,3	4,0
Understanding and defining social problems	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%	50,0%	4,5	4,5
Understanding and creating solutions to social problems	0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	50,0%	50,0%	4,5	4,5
(Social) Impact of a social enterprise	0,0%	0,0%	12,5%	37,5%	50,0%	4,4	4,5
Business model and its elements	0,0%	0,0%	37,5%	37,5%	25,0%	3,9	4,0
Total	0,0%	0,0%	12,5%	50,0%	37,5%	4,3	4,0

Table 4: Self-assessment on the level of knowledge of social entrepreneurship of the Latvian participants after training on the cycle 3.

The oral feedback confirmed these results, as according to the interviews and discussions, many participants had the opinion that the training had

increased their knowledge of entrepreneurship, as one Finnish young person expresses in the following interview extract:

Interviewer: *Did you have any knowledge of entrepreneurship beforehand when you came to the training?*

Participant: *Yes, I had some.*

Interviewer: *So, you didn't come from an empty table, so to say*

Participant: *No.*

Interviewer: *Did the training meet your expectations? Did you learn what you wanted to learn?*

Participant: *Yes, I do feel so. I learnt new things and could put effort into those things I wanted to learn more about.*

(Participant interview, male, 6.3.2025)

This interviewee attended the second training cycle in November-December 2024. He felt he had gained a lot from the training to strengthen his knowledge of entrepreneurship, as well as learn new things about social entrepreneurship. From this training, he had gotten the spark to develop innovative ideas for his own functioning enterprise. A few of the participants in the Social Business Academy had had education and training on entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship

before this training, or they studied fields in which similar types of tools for service design had been used. The previous experience and knowledge of the taught subjects influenced their willingness to educate themselves further in social entrepreneurship, whether the intention was to start an enterprise or adopt whole new ideas for their already functioning enterprises, as the participant presents in the following interview account:

Interviewer: What about the training in general? Do you feel you learnt what you wanted to learn?

Interviewee: Yes, I wanted to get crucial knowledge of what entrepreneurship is, and I think I got a very good scratch of the surface of what all entrepreneurship can entail. There were a lot of in-depth things that I would want to learn, but it was very good; I got a very good basis for it.

Interviewer: Was your own enterprise more like social entrepreneurship, or is it more traditional entrepreneurship?

Interviewee: Well, when I came there, I didn't have any other ideas than that I can't make art full-time because my hands get broken, but I want to do it in some way, so I had the idea of a side business, but it was not social in any way, I just thought I want to do this in some way in the future, at least part of the time. But now, after I took this training, I have thought of how I can get the social dimension there to go with the activity.

Interviewer: Okay, so it kind of lightened there.

(Participant interview, female, 3.3.2025)

As the participant explains, the training gave a lot of new knowledge and new insights on entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, also to develop the previous ideas further, to start an enterprise. According to the

participant feedback, the impacts of the training have been multifold and have emerged in unexpected contexts. Another interviewee said that even her father, who had thought of starting his own business, had been enthused by

the experiences of his daughter in the Social Business Academy:

Interviewer: Do you think it was useful for you to get employment in the future? Like, does it help that you have gone through the training, and how do you think the training will benefit you in the labour market in the future when you're looking for a job or something?

Participant: I think this is more helpful for people who are not looking for a job but are starting to look a bit, start a business, and this has been helpful in the sense that I can tell other people who already have business ideas to maybe look into the social aspects. For example, I talked today with my father. He wants to open a business, and he's been starting to think about the social business aspect because of this programme, so it has been great.

(Participant interview, female, 26.2.2025)

According to this experience and opinions on the usefulness of the training in the Social Business Academy, the employment aspect in the future doesn't appear as crucial as the fact that they have really learnt to open up a business with a social aspect involved. According to many, the training was not perceived as benefiting them directly in job-seeking or their employability, although passing the training is important in the CV, as it then tells that the jobseeker has done other things, too, than "spitting on the ceiling".

The same kind of opinions were common in e-survey feedback responses as well. The inability of many young people to see beforehand any direct benefits of this training for future working life seems understandable, as it is not clear how the training would help them to search for a regular job. Instead, the fact that the training would

contribute to their opportunities to be self-employed has been recognised as more apparent.

The general experiences regarding the training were also positive among those participants who did not have a secondary education degree. Although the theoretical knowledge provided in the training had sometimes been difficult to adopt, they were happy to have been involved in the programme. They also had a positive experience with the organisation of the training and the opportunity to travel. However, the requirement to operate in English during the joint activities had been an obstacle to learning for some, which sometimes made it difficult to participate in the activities.

In sum, taking all participant feedback into account, the training had positive effects both for those who had

more ground education to start working in the programme, and those who had less education. Some of the participants, such as those with a student status in a vocational university, could, for example, consider starting their own enterprise using the knowledge they gained from the basic training and mentoring in the Innovation Lab. Those with less formal education felt that the experience was valuable, and it was important for them to have managed to pass the training programme, and even to have expressed themselves in English, whenever it was requested. Thus, the dimension of participation seemed crucial, especially with the young people with less education.

Negative feedback dealt mostly with the practical organisation of the training, but there was variation between young people in terms of how it was perceived. For instance, group work functioned well with many participants, but some felt it blurred their own thinking. They would have wished for more individual work and support with their own business ideas. Furthermore, not all appreciated group work because the group dynamics usually functioned in favour of knowledgeable and talkative individuals, and some participants felt they were not able to express their thoughts or opinions.

Nevertheless, at the level of practical organisation, the group activities also worked in favour of those with learning difficulties in passing the training, as

nobody was penalised for not expressing their views in the group. However, group work arrangements disfavoured them in the sense of not encouraging them to learn individually and develop their own thinking.

The group tasks, which were not connected to social business ideation per se, were considered useless by some participants, and they felt those tasks took valuable time from more principal issues related to social entrepreneurship. Among some Finnish participants, there was the opinion that many group tasks and assignments were related to mere socialising. Gatherings to “get to know each other” were unnecessary and sometimes even embarrassing. Similarly, the activities intended to serve as icebreakers between Finns and Latvians were not perceived positively by all participants; according to some participants, the co-operation between the countries was minimal in any case regarding the ideation and developing the business ideas, as there were no transnational groups involved to do that.

On the practical level of the training implementation, there was more time involved for the participants to develop the business ideas during the training cycle 2. It was also reflected in the feedback, as the views were positive concerning the knowledge base and practical organisation of the training. During cycle 3, the general opinion expressed was that there had not been enough time to develop or discuss the

business ideas in groups, which affected the pitching of ideas.

Overall, the organisation of the training with external educators and expert speakers was considered outstanding, and these contributions were highly valued. For most, they had helped to develop themselves to think critically. In the case of Finland, the situation improved considerably in cycles 2 and 3, as they included more training in knowledge and skills for social entrepreneurship instead of entrepreneurship in general. The general knowledge

of entrepreneurship reflected straightforwardly the business ideas of the participants and didn't equip them with the knowledge of basic operations of social businesses to a sufficient extent, as could be seen in the e-survey feedback. During cycles 2 and 3, the trainers were more engaged with the core functioning of social enterprises, which could also be seen in the business ideas developed by the young people, as with the Finnish participants as well, they were carefully thought through with respect to the values of a social enterprise.

PART 3

Evaluation of the functionality and replicability of “Social Business Academy” and the wider societal impact of education in social entrepreneurship

In this part of the report, the evaluation of the project is presented in two crucial viewpoints, which are the functionality and replicability of the education in terms of young people involved, and the wider societal impact of this education relating to social entrepreneurship, especially in regard to the conditions of contemporary youth. Firstly, the outcomes of the project are evaluated in terms of its aims, as stated during the project's application phase. Secondly, the benefits of the education program are evaluated in terms of employment of young people and reflected in the current trends of their working life interests in contemporary culture, as well as the social change facing work and working life. The report concludes with general recommendations on how to promote the employability and self-employment of young people in terms of education for social entrepreneurship.

1. Evaluation of the project outcomes in terms of its original aims: NEETs and inclusivity

The basic aims of the project were to enhance the knowledge and skills of those young people, especially those who come from disadvantaged backgrounds. For example, if the educational background is not excellent, it influences their prospects for the future. The aim of the project was to reach out, for instance, to NEET young people (not in education, employment,

or training) and those young people who live in remote areas and thus have fewer opportunities.

These aims were not accomplished in the project in total. During the first training cycle, it was difficult to reach young people not in education, employment, or training. This was partly due to the methods of the recruitment process. For example, social media campaigns were used in both countries; although it was a successful way to find interested young people, there was a lot of variation in their social and educational backgrounds. In that respect, social media campaigns tempted young people with very varied skills and abilities to join the programme, such as university students, who are at a more advanced level to learn social entrepreneurship than those with less formal education. Visiting schools was another fruitful method to find participants, but due to the different levels of skills and abilities of these young people as well, some of them had better prospects for the future, such as plans for higher education. As a consequence, the participants had very different starting points with the training programme.

Professionals in youth services and outreach youth work were contacted as well to find suitable participants, but not many young people were reached that way. However, two persons found by outreach youth work dropped off voluntarily in Latvia after one day of attendance at the training.

It is well known in the youth field that NEET young people cannot be easily reached. There are several reasons for that, relating often to their social circumstances, but also the state of health, as the health condition is often not good enough to start with education. (E.g. Gallegos et al. 2023; Gretschel & Myllyniemi 2021.) Some may have learning difficulties, which is one of the most common reasons for NEET status. They might feel this type of education is unbeneficial for them if it appears to be too demanding.

According to the participation feedback of the first training cycle, there were huge differences among the attendees from Finland, such as how they felt they had learnt the basics of social entrepreneurship (see table 2). The number of those who found the training difficult was quite high, and according to the e-surveys, almost half of the participants in the first training cycle. The drop-offs and those who felt they had not learnt sufficiently might indicate that there have been difficulties in understanding the teaching, related to the advanced nature of the educational program. The provided theoretical knowledge was too demanding for some to adopt, although illustrative toolkits and gamification methods were often used to make complicated issues more understandable for young people.

Some attendees pointed out criticism towards the practice of mixing participants with a huge variation in their

educational backgrounds. Several attendants were university students, and some of them even had entrepreneurship as their main subject. Inevitably, they were at a more advanced level in their knowledge of entrepreneurship, compared with peers who did not have a secondary education. Some attendants felt that they had not received enough support in their studies, as, in their opinion, the difficulty level of the training corresponded to the level of knowledge of those who had better educational backgrounds.

Taking these dimensions into account, it would be worth considering assessing the learning needs of the participants before the training starts. The need for support of the participants should be assessed to plan support measures for each individual prior to starting the basic training. A practice of assessment and that of additional support in learning the basics of social entrepreneurship would be an important stage in designing the curriculum, so that each attendant could be properly advised throughout the training programme, and no one would feel like an outsider. The assessment could be, for instance, first included in the self-assessment e-survey concerning the level of knowledge and skills before the training, with a few questions added considering their need for support. Combined with that, the assessment could involve personal discussion with those participants who have indicated in the survey that they need additional support. During the personal

discussion, the trainer and the trainee could beforehand agree upon the supporting measures during the training, such as more thorough explanations or complementary tasks, for example.

According to education research, practices of support for learning should always be individual-based (e.g. Mclachlan & Davis, 2013). Assessment of the need for individual support in learning is a crucial practice in all official educational levels, for example, in Finland (Official Statistics of Finland, Support for Learning, read 4.4.2025). Most often, it is sufficient that additional support is provided in those subjects with which the student has challenges.

Social Business Academy was a non-formal, short-term and highly participatory educational programme in its design. The participants studied in groups, and the efforts of each participant were valuable to the group in developing a social business idea. Ample peer support was involved. The dimension of non-formal learning in a group of peers was very important in the programme, as the participants were able to make a collective effort to develop a business idea and learn from each other during the process. Additional support was provided by the trainers in the form of mentoring and giving advice on the business ideas of each group.

However, it was not individual support that could be offered by the trainers, although the group members were different in their abilities and introduced

very different aspects of their business ideas based on the level of their own knowledge and participation. The method often had the consequence that the group dynamics favoured the members with more ideas and good knowledge, and the need for support in understanding often remained unnoticed by the trainers. The dimension of non-formal learning in formal and informal learning settings has been widely recognised (e.g. Looney & Santibanez, 2021), and the importance of it can be noticed in the supporting structures of this training programme, such as mentoring involvement, peer support and facilitation. Nevertheless, the feedback from the training programme has indicated that additional individual support would have been useful for some of the participants.

Although inclusion in education is referred to as a practice, in which all are provided education according to the individual needs for support in learning, it has also been argued by the researchers that inclusive practice should enable all an equal opportunity for participation (Niemi & Mietola 2023). In this sense, the Social Business Academy was inclusive, as all interested young people were enabled to participate in the training if they fulfilled certain administrative criteria framed in the policies of the European Union. According to the participant feedback, some felt it was especially important to have been able to participate, although the difficult topics and the need to use English in joint events posed a big

challenge to understanding the teaching. However, despite the challenges in understanding, the experience of studying at the Social Business Academy has been remarkably positive and valuable. This feedback indicates the profound importance of the opportunity for participation, even though additional support was not provided because of the nature of the training methods, such as group work and other collective tasks.

Nevertheless, additional personal support is crucial in groups with considerable differences in the levels of knowledge and background education. As in the Social Business Academy, it was not possible to offer the training solely to NEET young people due to difficulties in reaching them. It is challenging to make modifications to the subjects of teaching, to the theoretical knowledge involved in it, and the training methods, to meet very different needs for support. This dilemma emerged already during the first planning discussions, when the project was started. The training curriculum of the Social Business Academy is advanced, but it might have better met the learning needs of those with a more formal education in their background.

These outcomes indicate that intersectional differences, such as differences in age, abilities, educational background and social conditions and circumstances between the participants were not taken into consideration to a

proper extent, when the training was designed and organised. The participants represented different ages with different life experiences, nationalities, native languages, educational backgrounds, and social circumstances, and potentially all these dimensions have affected their ability to understand the theoretically demanding issues. However, the programme of Social Business Academy reached inclusivity in the sense that it involved elements of practical learning facilitated, for example, by gamification and illustrative toolkits, so that it was accessible to all young people with different traits, abilities, and backgrounds could participate.

2. Evaluation of the project outcomes in terms of its original aims: enhancing young people's knowledge and skills for social entrepreneurship

The training provided in the Social Business Academy was perceived generally very positively by the young people. They mostly felt that the education programme provided sufficient knowledge on entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship, and the training was a spark for many to consider starting their own enterprise. The expertise of the trainers was considered excellent, and some even felt privileged to have been able to participate.

According to the self-assessment

surveys, approximately one-fifth of the participants of each training cycle assessed their own knowledge of entrepreneurship as good or excellent already before the training started. The result indicates that many young people are knowledgeable about the business world and the functioning of enterprises. However, there was variation between the participants regarding the sources of their knowledge: a few participants studied entrepreneurship at the university or vocational college or had attended educational courses on business, a few have entrepreneurial parents or families, and some are entrepreneurs themselves.

Although these backgrounds gave prospects convenient for some to study in the Social Business Academy, many of those already knowledgeable on entrepreneurship felt that the training provided a lot of new knowledge to them. The new knowledge was often related to social entrepreneurship, as for many participants, it had been unfamiliar. According to the feedback, social entrepreneurship was more familiar to Latvians than Finns, the reason for which might lie in cultural differences relating to business and self-employment. The researchers argue that in Latvia, knowledge on entrepreneurship is provided at all educational levels (Vevere et al. 2021), whereas in Finland, many young people feel that the knowledge is not provided sufficiently in comprehensive and secondary education (Haikkola & Myllyniemi 2019).

These differences between the countries further indicate that the Finns grow in a working-life culture of paid jobs and regular employment, which appears to be more traditional than that of the Latvians, who are more open to alternative possibilities. A few studies support these interpretations, as in relation to the formation of welfare systems, the culture of social entrepreneurship is quite different in the Baltic countries than in Nordic countries. Innovativeness is emphasised in Baltic cultures of social entrepreneurship, whereas Finland represents the Nordic welfare state model in this respect, as the trust in the welfare state and institutions to solve social problems is at a high level in Finland. That not only reflects on the lesser understanding of the value of social entrepreneurship as an option to promote wellbeing, but also influences whether it is comprehended as a viable option to earn a living. (Lindberg & Kostilainen 2021.) Another crucial reason for Finnish young people to be more cautious about becoming entrepreneurs is the strict employment and unemployment policies, according to which unemployment beneficiaries could be easily lost if a person indicates having a private enterprise, even if it is not generating a profit. These strict policies do not encourage unemployed young people to become entrepreneurs in Finland. (E.g. Mononen-Batista - Costa & Brunila 2016.)

Overall, the training curriculum of Social Business Academy has promoted

the knowledge and skills of young people to become social entrepreneurs, and thus, SocEntYouth has been a highly successful project in this initial sense. Most attendants have been very content with their participation, and most are eager to learn more about social entrepreneurship.

The fact that social entrepreneurship is factually entrepreneurship has been addressed in the topics on which the training sessions have focused. For example, during the first cycle, in Finnish Bootcamp sessions, the training was divided to deal with both entrepreneurship in general and social entrepreneurship in particular, but a vast amount of attention was paid to advising young people to start up an enterprise. That influenced the participants to the extent that many of the business ideas the young people developed in groups were not exactly social enterprises. When they pitched their ideas in joint events, many comments from the audience dealt with the need for them to clarify the dimension of the social worth or impact of their business ideas. However, this outcome with Finnish participants was taken into account and changed in the design and implementation of training for the second and third training cycles.

Simultaneously, some participants of the Latvian first training cycle had been complaining that insufficient knowledge was provided on entrepreneurship in general, including financial planning. In Latvia, the focus of the

training had been strictly on social entrepreneurship, and some participants felt they would have benefited from a more profound knowledge of the general functioning of enterprises.

Despite these differences in the details of the taught subjects, the teaching of social entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship provided in the Social Business Academy has been considered by young people to be of excellent quality and useful for their future, which is aligned with the original aims of the project. As with the functionality of the training, nothing crucial has emerged as necessary to change considering the operations or activities of the curriculum, except paying more attention in implementation to the balance of handling entrepreneurship on the one hand and social entrepreneurship on the other hand. When marketing the training for young people to recruit them, this balance should already be handled in meaningful ways to avoid misconceptions or disappointments.

The replicability of the project is good. The participants warmly welcomed the contribution of external experts, and it strengthened the knowledge base of entrepreneurship provided in the education and the taught subjects. The trainers who belonged to the project staff had particularly good participant feedback as well, and in terms of replicability, the qualifications of the training staff should be maintained and secured in the future. Some of the trainers and external trainers have

PhD degrees in Economics or relevant fields, which has been one of the benefits of the Social Business Academy to ensure the quality of teaching.

However, despite the indisputable indications of the quality of the training, there are a few dimensions that could be considered in terms of the replicability of the training programme. Firstly, when recruiting young people, the intersectional differences should be considered so that the content of the training programme could be modified in advance according to, for instance, young people's age or educational backgrounds. Alternatively, the potential need for support should be assessed for each participant individually beforehand so that additional support could be provided during the training.

3. Evaluation of the project outcomes: Young people's entrepreneurial interests triggering change in youth employment

The business ideas that the participants developed in the training programme were multiple and often very imaginative. There were a few traditional business ideas presented, such as a car sales company, but most of the ideas indicated a sophisticated understanding of social entrepreneurship. Amongst the social business ideas of many groups of participants, the social value or worth was thoroughly incorporated into the business activity.

Young people introduced, for example, ideas for social enterprises promoting inclusive sports and art therapy for vulnerable youth. The fields of the ideas for social businesses were multiple, and they entailed at least the fields of manufacturing, art and fashion, environmental sustainability, sports, beauty and wellbeing, education, digital services, and social services, such as children, elderly and disability care, as well as youth work.

The training program evolved throughout the three cycles in terms of the teaching methods and practical advising in social entrepreneurship. As the teaching concentrated mostly on social entrepreneurship in the second and third training cycles, much improvement among the participants could be noticed by the end of the programme. It reflected on the social business models of the participants, as they were thoroughly thought out and presented.

Digital solutions were often used in the ideas to help vulnerable groups of people, which was the basic social aim of several business models. Many participants also took advantage of their artistic interests in the ideation of their social businesses. Several types of arts were represented in the ideas, such as arty handicrafts, visual art, both digital and painted, and manufacturing theatre equipment.

The use of digital solutions and art in the business ideation of the

participants aligns with the current trends in entrepreneurship of young people, as many young start-up entrepreneurs have taken advantage of digitalisation and their own artistic hobbies as the core activities of their enterprises (Berg & Ylöstalo 2019). This trend has contributed to one of the most impactful changes in the working life of young people, as different forms of self-employment have become more tempting, triggered by the promise of the opportunity to use their own creative interests.

This trend further contributes to the vast social change concerning the employment futures of young people, when the decrease of traditional industrial jobs and the increase of the need for knowledge in work have influenced employment markets. As for young people, the decrease in traditional employment is leading to the increasing precarity of working life, and the growing need for alternative options, such as self-employment, is one of the main consequences of this development. (e.g. Furlong & Cartmel 2007; Haikkola & Myllyniemi 2019.)

Many of the participants of the Social Business Academy did not have the opinion that the training would directly benefit them in seeking work in the future. The response option in the e-survey was defined in a way that they were not able to tell exactly why they felt that way. Enhancing their employability by promoting their entrepreneurial and soft skills was stated as one of

the aims of the SocEntYouth project, but no direct ways were indicated that the knowledge and skills they learned would benefit them in job-seeking. Possibly, the impacts of the training on seeking work, whether they are direct or indirect, have not yet been seen, and it is too early for young people to consider that. Instead, the benefits of the training for starting their own business activities could be directly seen, and thus the impact of the training could be considered to relate to their increased skills for self-employment.

Amid the situation affected by the changes in working life and employment, young people are forced to adjust to the growing demand for their own initiative solutions, considering their employment, especially if their current education (or lack of it) doesn't meet the requirements for jobs. Social Business Academy has revealed a crucial dimension regarding the influential social change that young people face in the contemporary working life culture, as it has shown their interest in different digital and artistic opportunities and offered them the possibility to harness their individual creativity and self-directedness into resources supporting their own employment and employability.

It is especially important that there has emerged the opportunity to channel individual artistic creativity into employment purposes. The training in Social Business Academy has enabled young people to let their imagination run wild

to innovate possibilities for entrepreneurship, and that alone has opened their minds to the world of opportunities - given the circumstances, that there is strong demand in Europe for new ideas and initiative, as the needs of young people are not necessarily met in the contemporary labour markets.

Particularly, it is important in the field of arts, in which the current provision of employment is not sufficient to cover the need for jobs corresponding to education. Several young people have university degrees or vocational education in artistic fields, and the possibility of starting an enterprise and becoming employed in these fields is an important societal impact of the Social Business Academy programme. The training has offered tools to channel artistic interests and creativity in exhilarating and meaningful ways to use them for entrepreneurial endeavours, which is utterly crucial in contemporary working life amid the vast structural changes in work.

Another remarkable societal impact of the Social Business Academy is its potential to promote sustainable working life and economies. Within the value base of social entrepreneurship, it is emphasised that the enterprise does not function only to grow financial profit, but to allocate the profit for either improving employment possibilities of those having difficulties to get employment, or to help and support vulnerable groups of people by providing them

with activities and services. These social values are crucial in the form of entrepreneurship, and helping these potential young entrepreneurs to scrutinise how social impact and the value of the common good are supported in the business world is essential. These important consequences of the training contribute to the maintenance of societal, economic, and climate-related sustainability and thus foster well-being in European societies, which ultimately strengthens their resilience.

4. Recommendations considering the educational programmes in the promotion of employability and self-employment of young people based on the experiences of implementing the SocEntYouth project

The definition of social entrepreneurship should be provided already when marketing the training for young people, so that they would have the right expectations for the training before it starts. The aspect of improvement of employability and working-life knowledge and skills, as well as the aspect of self-employment, should be defined and emphasised in the marketing of the training, in addition to the promise of the improvement of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills, so that the multiple benefits of taking the training would be understood beforehand. During the implementation of the

training, it should be explained how social entrepreneurship differs from regular entrepreneurship in order to avoid misunderstandings concerning the nature and the benefits of the knowledge and skills that the training is actually providing.

Intersectional differences among young people should be recognised when planning and implementing educational programmes for youth, especially if the intention is to enhance the employment prospects and opportunities for young people, especially in vulnerable positions. For example, disability and illness, socio-economic and socio-demographic deprivation, lack of formal education or migrant status can influence abilities to adopt knowledge and skills. Therefore, the educational programmes should be accessible in their content, teaching and visualising, and additional support should be provided for those needing it. In order to ensure the accessibility of the training, there should be modifications implemented for the curriculum according to the ground education and educational level of the participants.

Quality in training should be maintained and secured with all trainers included in the programme. Examples

of currently operating enterprises and practical knowledge relating to their activities should be included in the programme in order for the young people to understand the operations of enterprises. The practical level of teaching is particularly important for those young people who have learning difficulties. It should also be ensured that the trainers have the abilities and necessary time resources to take the different learning needs into account while implementing the programme.

The target group of the educational programme ought to be carefully considered, so that the differences between the young people and their abilities to adopt knowledge would be more manageable in the design and implementation of the training. However, the inclusivity should also be considered beforehand and thought over, what kind of applicants should be included to take the training, or when it is more appropriate to consider the exclusion of some applicants. For instance, if the training is targeted at young people in a vulnerable position, it might not be appropriate to include university students or those with better future prospects in the same group, also to avoid discrimination in the training setting.

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Tables

Table 1: The teaching met my goals and learning needs. Feedback questionnaire for participants in Finland and Latvia, Cycle 1.

Table 2: I learnt the basic principles of the aims and operations of a social enterprise. Feedback questionnaire for participants in Finland and Latvia, Cycle 1.

Table 3: Self-assessment on the level of knowledge in social entrepreneurship of Finnish participants after the training, Cycle 2.

Table 4: Self-assessment on the level of knowledge of social entrepreneurship of Latvian participants, after the training, Cycle 3.

Appendixes

Appendix 1: Self-assessment e-questionnaire.

Appendix 2: Feedback on Bootcamp Onsite.

Appendix 3: Feedback on Bootcamp Online.

Appendix 4: Feedback on Bootcamp Onsite and Online.

Appendix 1

Interreg

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Social Business Academy: My knowledge and skills before the training

Social Entrepreneurship

Assess your current knowledge on the following issues (1=little or no knowledge; 2=some knowledge; 3=mediocre knowledge; 4=good knowledge; 5=excellent knowledge):

	1	2	3	4	5
Business and enterprises in general	<input type="radio"/>				
Social enterprise in general	<input type="radio"/>				
Difference between entrepreneurship and social entrepreneurship	<input type="radio"/>				
Clientele relevant to a social enterprise	<input type="radio"/>				
Understanding and defining social problems	<input type="radio"/>				
Understanding and creating ways to solve social problems	<input type="radio"/>				
(Social) value or worth generated by a social enterprise	<input type="radio"/>				
Business model and its components	<input type="radio"/>				

Employability skills

Assess your current skills in the following (1=poor or no skills; 2=some skills; 3=mediocre skills; 4=good skills; 5=excellent skills):

	1	2	3	4	5
Problem solving skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Skills in initiating things independently	<input type="radio"/>				
Skills in recognition of your own strengths and weaknesses (in work/studies)	<input type="radio"/>				
Leadership skills (to take up a project and lead it)	<input type="radio"/>				
Teamwork skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpersonal skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Intercultural skills (to function in culturally diverse communities)	<input type="radio"/>				
Foreign language skills	<input type="radio"/>				

Appendix 2

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Social Business Academy: Feedback on Bootcamp onsite training

Evaluate on the scale from 1 to 5, what do you think about the following (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
The training met my aims and needs to learn.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the distinction between an enterprise and a social enterprise.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the basic principles of the aims and functioning of a social enterprise.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to create a business model canvas.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to define the value propositions of my business model.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to consider the key functions, crucial collaborators and the financial structure of my business model.	<input type="radio"/>				

The training provided me sufficient knowledge and practical tools to (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
Recognise a suitable group of beneficiaries	<input type="radio"/>				
Think and formulate a solvable problem	<input type="radio"/>				
Plan efficient solutions to solve the problem	<input type="radio"/>				
Test the functionality of the solution I came up with	<input type="radio"/>				

Give your opinion on the following (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
The training was so good, that I am considering to start my own social enterprise	<input type="radio"/>				
Used concepts were clear and understandable	<input type="radio"/>				
Training materials were multiple and sufficient	<input type="radio"/>				
I would have needed more time to internalize what I learnt	<input type="radio"/>				
Training increased my knowledge and skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Training is beneficial for me if I am applying for a job	<input type="radio"/>				
I am eager to get more training in these issues	<input type="radio"/>				

Other remarks on the training:

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Social Business Academy

Feedback Questionnaire on Bootcamp Online Training

1. Evaluate your impressions on the following on the scale from 1 to 5 (1= I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
I learnt to map a social problem and its consequences and root causes.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to define my problem statement.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to validate my problem statement.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the difference between a customer and a beneficiary.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to create a beneficiary, who benefits the most from my business idea.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to define the main root causes of the problem I want to solve.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the basics of key insight map with solution characteristics and requirements, to help to create a solution to a problem.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the basics of S.C.A.M.P.E.R. method to create a solution to a problem.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to make a solution description.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to make a risk analysis for my business idea.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to make a prototyping plan to my business idea.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to create an updated version of my business model canvas by using the elements taught in the training.	<input type="radio"/>				

2. Give your opinion on the following (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
The training was so good, that I am considering to start my own social enterprise.	<input type="radio"/>				
Used concepts were clear and understandable.	<input type="radio"/>				
Training materials were multiple and sufficient.	<input type="radio"/>				
I would have needed more time to internalize what I learnt.	<input type="radio"/>				
Training increased my knowledge and skills.	<input type="radio"/>				
Training is beneficial for me if I am applying for a job.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am eager to get more training in these issues.	<input type="radio"/>				

3. Other remarks on the training:

Central Baltic Programme

Social Business Academy: Feedback on Bootcamp onsite training

Evaluate on the scale from 1 to 5, what do you think about the following (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
The training met my aims and needs to learn.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the distinction between an enterprise and a social enterprise.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt the basic principles of the aims and functioning of a social enterprise.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to create a business model canvas.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to define the value propositions of my business model.	<input type="radio"/>				
I learnt to consider the key functions, crucial collaborators and the financial structure of my business model.	<input type="radio"/>				

The training provided me sufficient knowledge and practical tools to (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
Recognise a suitable group of beneficiaries	<input type="radio"/>				
Think and formulate a solvable problem	<input type="radio"/>				
Plan efficient solutions to solve the problem	<input type="radio"/>				
Test the functionality of the solution I came up with	<input type="radio"/>				

Give your opinion on the following (1 = I agree; 2 = I somewhat agree; 3 = I don't know; 4 = I somewhat disagree; 5 = I disagree):

	1	2	3	4	5
The training was so good, that I am considering to start my own social enterprise	<input type="radio"/>				
Used concepts were clear and understandable	<input type="radio"/>				
Training materials were multiple and sufficient	<input type="radio"/>				
I would have needed more time to internalize what I learnt	<input type="radio"/>				
Training increased my knowledge and skills	<input type="radio"/>				
Training is beneficial for me if I am applying for a job	<input type="radio"/>				
I am eager to get more training in these issues	<input type="radio"/>				

Other remarks on the training:
